

Kinetics of palladium(II)-catalyzed oxidation of sulfur(IV) by oxygen[†]

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Abstract : The kinetics of the palladium(II) catalyzed autoxidation of sulfur(IV) has been studied using stopped flow spectrophotometric and conventional techniques. The observed kinetics is in agreement with the rate law

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_3 [\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2 [\text{O}_2] [\text{H}^+]^{-1}$$

The stability constant for the formation of the complex $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_3]^{4-}$ from $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_2]^{2-}$ and HSO_3^- ions has been determined spectrophotometrically. The values of k_1 , k_{II} and k_{III} relating to following scheme have been determined from stopped-flow study.

C_1 appears to be intermediate of the type - $\{[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_n]^{(2n-2)-}[\text{O}_2]\}$ - in which O_2 is weakly bonded to axial position and one sulfite group appears to be O-bonded instead of S-bonded. Subsequently, O_2 moves to square plane and therefore intra-molecular rearrangement converts O-bonded complex into S-bonded complex. Following mechanism has been proposed to explain the autoxidation kinetics.

The effect of NH_3 , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and C_6H_6 has also been studied.

Keywords : Kinetics, sulfur(IV), palladium(II), oxygen, catalysis, ammonia, ethanol, benzene.

Introduction

Transition metals are effective catalysts for catalyzing the autoxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide¹⁻⁸. Among the elements of first transition series, the catalysis by Mn^{II} ⁹, $\text{Fe}^{\text{II/III}}$ ¹⁰, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} ¹¹ and Cu^{II} ¹² has been the subject of numerous studies. The oxides of these metals are also known to catalyze autoxidation of sulfur(IV) heterogeneously^{1,2}. The catalysis by both the metal ions and metal oxide surface requires the coordination of both S^{IV} and O_2 to the metal ion/particle surface. The coordination of both S^{IV} and O_2 activates them and the ability of the transition metals to exhibit multiple oxidation states help

in electron transfer¹⁻⁸. For these catalytic reactions, both radical and non-radical mechanisms have been proposed¹⁻⁸.

A literature survey reveals the lack of studies on the catalytic role of the metals of second transition series in sulfur(IV) autoxidation, although a large number of Pd^{II} -catalyzed reactions have been the subject of study¹³. This led us to study catalytic role of palladium(II). Incidentally, Mahal and van Eldic¹⁴ have indicated palladium(II) to be a catalyst for the autoxidation of S^{IV} . Further, sulfotriquo palladium(II) complex is reported to be thermally unstable and decompose slowly to Pd^{II} and sulfuric acid¹⁵. The kinetics of formation and the reactivity of the

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complex $\text{Pd}(\text{Et}_4\text{dien})\text{SO}_3$ (Et_4dien = 1,1,7,7-tetraethyl-diethylenetriamine) has also been studied in detail as a function of pH, $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$, temperature and pressure¹⁶.

We, in this chapter, report the results of our spectrophotometric and stopped flow studies on the formation and decomposition of sulfitotripalladium(II) complexes. The kinetics of Pd^{II} -catalyzed autoxidation is also reported.

Experimental

Stock solution of palladium(II) was prepared by dissolving PdCl_2 in about 0.14 mol L^{-1} hydrochloric acid. Acetate buffer was used for maintaining pH of the reaction mixture. For this purpose, 10 cm^3 of acetate buffer made from $2.0 \text{ M CH}_3\text{COOH}$ and $2.0 \text{ M CH}_3\text{COONa}$ in different proportions as per requirement were added to the reaction mixture (total volume 100 cm^3) for obtaining the desired pH. The experimental procedure, which was exactly the same as described earlier by Brodzinsky *et al.*¹⁷ and subsequently used by us^{18,19}, is given here in brief.

The reactions were conducted in 0.15 L Erlenmeyer flasks, open to air, to allow the passage of atmospheric oxygen. The flask was placed in a beaker, which had an inlet at the lower part and an outlet at the upper part for circulating thermostated water for maintaining desired temperature, $30.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The reactions were initiated by adding the desired volume of freshly prepared standard Na_2SO_3 solution to the reaction mixture containing other additives such as buffer, catalyst, etc. The reaction mixture was stirred continuously and magnetically at $1600 \pm 100 \text{ rpm}$ to allow the passage of atmospheric oxygen.

The kinetics was followed by determining the unreacted sulfur(IV) iodometrically in a slightly acidic medium^{18,19}. For this purpose, 5.0 ml aliquot samples were withdrawn periodically and added to a titration flask containing known quantity of iodine and sufficient acetic acid to make the medium acidic. The unreacted iodine was titrated with standard sodium thiosulfate solution using starch as an indicator.

Spectrophotometric measurements :

UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded on Hitachi U-2000 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Cells of 1.0 cm path length were used and maintained at desired temperature ($\pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) by circulating thermostated water.

Stopped flow equipment :

The rates of formation and decomposition of $\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}\text{-S}^{\text{IV}}$ complexes were studied on Hi-Tech Scientific Stopped-Flow Equipment (PQ/SF-53) which was completely com-

puter controlled. This equipment gives transmittance in terms of volts. The sweep time selection depends upon the fastness of the reaction. The data processing unit directly gave pseudo-first order rate constant. There was arrangement for controlling the temperature ($\pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) of reaction cell. When it was desired to exclude oxygen, nitrogen was continuously bubbled in the stock solution before using them for stopped-flow studies. Each run was repeated at least four times and the values reported henceforth are the average of these replicates measurements.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

A product analysis showed sulfate to be only oxidation product, which was estimated gravimetrically by precipitating it as BaSO_4 using the standard procedure. The sulfate recovery from the reaction mixture after the completion of the reaction was $\sim 97 \pm 1\%$. The stoichiometry of the reaction, therefore, can be represented as in eq. (1).

Results

Spectrophotometric study of palladium(II)-sulfur(IV) complex formation :

The spectrum of palladium chloride in acetate buffered solution is shown in Fig. 1. Chloro complexes ($[\text{Pd}(\text{Cl})_n]^{(2-n)+}$, $K_1 = 2.18 \times 10^4$, $K_2 = 3.46 \times 10^3$, K_3

Fig. 1. Spectrum of palladium chloride in acetate buffer at pH = 5.22 and $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$: (a) in absence of S^{IV} and (b) in presence of S^{IV} .

$= 4.78 \times 10^2$, $K_4 = 47.8$) are known to be weaker than acetate complexes ($[\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_n]^{(2-n)+}$, $K_1 = 1.0 \times 10^6$, $K_2 = 3.98 \times 10^4$, $K_3 = 3.16 \times 10^2$, $K_4 = 1.0 \times 10^2$)²⁰. The latter seems to absorb strongly at 245 nm . The high concentration of acetate ions (0.18 mol L^{-1}) and the high

stability constants of $[\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_n]^{(2-n)+}$ ensure that palladium(II) will largely exist as acetate complexes.

The addition of sodium sulfite to buffered palladium(II) solution results in the immediate appearance of peaks at 310 nm and 245 ± 1 nm and a shoulder at 365 nm (Fig. 1). When the $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ is increased, the absorbance at 310 nm increases but the absorbance at 365 nm remains largely unaffected. Further two isosbestic points are seen in Fig. 2 suggesting strongly that one complex is being replaced by another. Mahal and van Eldik^{17,19} have reported the spectral characteristics of sulfite-palladium(II)

Fig. 2. The change in absorbance of $\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}\text{-S}^{\text{IV}}$ complex on increasing $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ at $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.22$ and 30°C : (a) $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (b) $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (c) $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (d) $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

complexes. The complex $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_2]^{2-}$ is reported to exhibit absorption maxima at 251 nm and 363 nm, whereas $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_3]^{4-}$ exhibits a characteristic absorption peak at 309 nm. Both these complexes have almost identical absorption at 251 nm. Thus, in our system the spectral characteristics suggest that both $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_3]^{4-}$ complexes must be present and, on increasing $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ more of trisulfitepalladium(II) complex is formed.

The results at different $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ were analyzed in terms of the following eq. (2)^{21,22} at constant pH and acetate.

$$A = -K^{-1}(A - A_0)/[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^n + A_\alpha \quad (2)$$

where A = absorbance of a $\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}\text{-S}^{\text{IV}}$ complex, A_α = absorbance when all palladium(II) was complexed, A_0 = absorbance of Pd^{II} in absence of S^{IV} and K = stability constant defined by eq. (3).

$$K = \frac{[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_3]^{4-}}{[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_2]^{2-} [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]} \quad (3)$$

Since Pd^{II} ion alone, in absence of S^{IV} , has no absorbance at 310 nm, hence A_0 is zero and so eq. (2) modifies to eq. (4),

$$1/A = 1/A_\alpha + 1/K [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^n A_\alpha \quad (4)$$

In accordance with eq. (4) and when $n = 1$, the plots between $1/A$ and $1/[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ were linear (Fig. 3). The values of K were found to be 55.2 and 98.0 at $\text{pH} 4.90$ and

Fig. 3. Determination of equilibrium constant K at different pH at $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}] = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 30°C : (o) $\text{pH} = 5.22$; (Δ) $\text{pH} = 4.90$.

5.22, respectively. The values of K are seen to be pH-dependent. On increasing pH the absorbance at 310 nm is seen to increase and the shoulder at 365 nm is seen to disappear. Obviously, higher pH favors the formation of $[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_3]^{4-}$. The sulfite ion concentration is related to total $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ by eq. (5),

$$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = \frac{[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2/K_{d_1}K_{d_2} + [\text{H}^+]/K_{d_2} + 1} \quad (5)$$

where K_{d_1} and K_{d_2} are the first and second dissociation constants of $\text{SO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$. The reported values¹ of K_{d_1} and K_{d_2} are 1.26×10^{-2} and 5.0×10^{-7} , respectively. In the pH range of this study eq. (5) will reduce to

$$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = \frac{K_{d_2} [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (6)$$

On substituting eq. (6) into (3), we get

Fig. 4. Change in absorbance with time at different wavelength at $[S^{IV}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Pd^{II}] = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.22$ and 30°C : (a) $\lambda = 310 \text{ nm}$, (b) $\lambda = 366 \text{ nm}$.

$$\frac{K[H^+]}{K_{d_2}} = \frac{[Pd(SO_3)_4]^{4-}}{[Pd(SO_3)_3]^{2-}[SO_3^{2-}]} = K_1 \quad (7)$$

From the values of K determined at $\text{pH} 4.90$ and 5.22 , K_1 values are found to be 1.39×10^2 at $\text{pH} 4.90$ and 1.20×10^2 at $\text{pH} 5.22$, which are seen to be in agreement.

It should be pointed out that the absorbance was unaffected by a change in [buffer], showing that acetate ions are not involved in complexation equilibria. It appears that addition of sulfite to a solution of acetatopalladium(II) complexes results in the formation of $[Pd(SO_3)_2]^{2-}$ and $[Pd(SO_3)_3]^{4-}$. The acetate ions are lost rapidly due to strong trans-labilizing effect of sulfite ions²³. Thus, these complexes are in fact $[Pd(H_2O)_2(SO_3)_2]^{2-}$ and $[Pd(H_2O)(SO_3)_3]^{4-}$. The absorbance measurement at 310 nm and 365 nm on Pd^{II} - S^{IV} system in N_2 -saturated, air-saturated and O_2 -saturated show that the presence and the absence of oxygen has no significant effect of $[O_2]$. This probably indicate that spectral characteristics of oxygenated Pd^{II} - S^{IV} complexes are not much different. Similar kind of observations have been noted in case of sulfite-iron(III) complexes by Kraft and van Eldik²⁴.

Time scanning experiments :

Since the main purpose of this study was to investigate Pd^{II} -catalysis in the autoxidation of S^{IV} , the absorbance changes at 310 nm and 365 nm in solution containing Pd^{II} , S^{IV} and O_2 were recorded with respect to time (Fig. 4). Whereas, there was little change in absorbance at 365 nm, the absorbance at 310 nm showed a decrease.

This probably shows that the reactive complex in the autoxidation reaction is $[Pd(SO_3)_3]^{4-}$.

A similar behavior was observed in autoxidation study (Fig. 5) which was conducted in stirred solutions containing Pd^{II} , S^{IV} and O_2 . The spectrum was recorded immediately after the initiation of the reaction, midway and

Fig. 5. The spectra of Pd^{II} - S^{IV} reaction mixture for autoxidation study at different times at $\text{pH} = 5.22$ and 30°C : (A) $PdCl_2$ alone, (B) Reaction mixture - Immediately after mixing Pd^{II} and S^{IV} , (C) After 10 min and (D) After completion of the reaction.

finally at the end of the reaction. Initially a large absorbance is seen at 310 nm and 365 nm. However at the end of the reaction, the large absorbance is seen only at 365 nm and the absorbance at 310 nm to be small, indicating $[Pd(SO_3)_3]^{4-}$ to be reactive.

Kinetics of formation and decomposition of sulfite-palladium(II) complexes :

The kinetics measurements, done on stopped flow equipment, were made by following the absorbance changes at 365 nm. These results showed the existence of at least three paths as shown in Fig. 6. The first path could be detected only at low $[Pd^{II}]$, i.e. in the range $1 \times 10^{-8} - 5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_1 , for this path did not depend on $[S^{IV}]$, pH and [buffer] (Table 1). However, k_1 increased on increasing $[O_2]$. In air and O_2 -saturated solutions, the values of k_1 were found to be 22 and 89 s^{-1} respectively. From these two values, an order of 0.89 in O_2 was calculated.

As shown in Fig. 6, the first path is followed by a second path. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{II} , for the second path did not depend up on pH , [buffer], $[O_2]$, [chloride] and $[S^{IV}]$. The values of k_{II} given in Table 2. The second path is followed by a third much slower reac-

Table 1. Values of k_I at different $[Pd^{II}]$, $[S^{IV}]$, pH and temperature

$10^7 [Pd^{II}]$ (mol L ⁻¹)	$10^3 [S^{IV}]$ (mol L ⁻¹)	t (°C)	pH	k_I (s ⁻¹)
	Air-saturated	(20% O ₂)		
0.5	0.5	30	5.22	19.60
0.8	0.5	30	5.22	22.90
1.0	0.5	30	5.22	21.70
2.0	0.5	30	5.22	20.20
5.0	0.5	30	5.22	21.30
10.0	0.5	30	5.22	22.20
1.0	0.1	30	5.22	22.80
1.0	0.1	30	5.22	19.90
1.0	0.1	30	5.22	20.80
1.0	0.1	30	5.22	21.90
1.0	0.1	30	5.22	21.80
1.0	0.5	30	4.80	20.80
1.0	0.5	30	4.95	18.50
1.0	0.5	30	5.29	20.50
1.0	0.5	30	5.65	22.50
1.0	0.5	30	5.80	21.70
1.0	0.5	20	5.22	19.07
1.0	0.5	25	5.22	23.50
1.0	0.5	30	5.22	25.70
1.0	0.5	35	5.22	29.30
	O ₂ -saturated	(100% O ₂)		
1.0	0.5	30	5.22	89.0

Table 2. Values of k_{II} at different $[Pd^{II}]$, $[S^{IV}]$, pH and temperature

$10^7 [Pd^{II}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 [S^{IV}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	t (°C)	pH	k_{II} (s ⁻¹)
0.5	0.5	30	5.22	27.5
1.0	0.5	30	5.22	26.7
2.5	0.5	30	5.22	28.2
5.0	0.5	30	5.22	28.4
10.0	0.5	30	5.22	26.4
5.0	0.5	20	5.22	24.6
5.0	2.5	20	5.22	26.8
5.0	5.0	20	5.22	29.3
5.0	25.0	20	5.22	51.2
5.0	0.5	25	5.22	26.6
5.0	2.5	25	5.22	28.7
5.0	2.5	30	5.22	29.3
5.0	5.0	30	5.22	36.2
5.0	0.5	35	5.22	31.5
5.0	0.5	35	5.22	35.0
5.0	2.5	35	5.22	39.5
5.0	5.0	35	5.22	25.4
5.0	0.5	30	4.50	26.7
5.0	0.5	30	4.80	26.5
5.0	0.5	30	4.95	27.5
5.0	0.5	30	5.22	26.1

Table 3. Values of k_{III} at different $[Pd^{II}]$, $[S^{IV}]$, pH and temperature

$10^7 [Pd^{II}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 [S^{IV}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	t (°C)	pH	k_{III} (s ⁻¹)
0.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.28
1.0	5.0	30	5.22	5.12
2.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.24
5.0	5.0	30	5.22	5.30
25.0	5.0	30	5.22	5.40
50.0	0.5	30	5.22	5.15
0.5	0.75	30	5.22	5.20
0.5	1.0	30	5.22	5.40
0.5	2.5	30	5.22	5.10
0.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.20
0.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.00
0.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.00
0.5	5.0	30	4.50	5.10
0.5	5.0	30	4.80	5.20
0.5	5.0	30	4.95	5.50
0.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.10
0.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.00
0.5	5.0	30	5.67	5.00
0.5	5.0	30	5.67	4.70
0.5	5.0	20	5.22	5.10
0.5	5.0	25	5.22	5.20
0.5	5.0	30	5.22	5.20
0.5	5.0	35	5.22	5.10

Fig. 6. The stopped flow trace showing the three steps simultaneously at $[Pd^{II}] = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³, $[S^{IV}] = 5 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, pH = 5.22 and 30 °C

tion which was independent of $[S^{IV}]$, pH, [buffer], [chloride] and $[O_2]$. The values of k_{III} are given in Table 3.

The results suggests that in the first step an intermediate, involving some Pd^{II}-sulfite complex and O₂, is formed. Subsequent two paths appear to involve isomerization/

rearrangement as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

C_1 appears to be intermediate of the type $\{[\text{Pd}(\text{SO}_3)_n]^{(2n-2)-}[\text{O}_2]\}$ - in which O_2 is weakly bonded to axial position and one sulfite group appears to be O-bonded instead of S-bonded. It is interesting to point out that in the reaction of sulfite with *trans*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en}(\text{OH})_2)]^{2+}$ and *trans*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en}_2(\text{OH})_2)(\text{SO}_3)]^+$, complex²⁵ the formation of O-bonded intermediate has been suggested. Subsequently, O_2 moves to square plane²⁶ and then an intramolecular rearrangement converts O-bonded complex into S-bonded complex.

Autoxidation kinetics :

Preliminary investigations : A preliminary study on the effect of [buffer] on reaction rate, examined by carrying out a four-fold variation in $[\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}]$ and $[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]$, in such a way that the ratio of $[\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}]/[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]$ and hence pH remained fixed, showed the rate to decrease only slightly (20%). The variations in ionic strength (0.1–1.0 mol dm⁻³) with the help of sodium perchlorate, and in chloride concentration (1×10^5 – 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) with the help of sodium chloride did not affect the rate to any significant extent.

Rate law : The reaction rate displayed a second order dependence on $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ defined by eq. (8).

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k_1[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2 \quad (8)$$

The values of second order rate constants, k_1 , were obtained by plotting $1/[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ versus time, t , as shown in Fig. 8. Second order plot at $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 4 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}] = 8 \times$

Fig. 7. Second order plot at $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 4 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}] = 8 \times 10^{-6}$ mol L⁻¹, pH = 5.04, $t = 30$ °C.

Fig. 8. The variation of k_1 with $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}]$ at pH = 5.22 and 30 °C.

10^{-6} mol L⁻¹, pH = 5.04, $t = 30$ °C.

The values k_1 determined at different $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}]$ showed a first order dependence in $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}]$ (Fig. 9) in agreement with the rate law :

$$k_1 = k_2[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}] \quad (9)$$

The value of k_2 from the plot in Fig. 9 was found to be 1.53×10^4 L² mol⁻² s⁻¹ at 30 °C and 5.22 pH.

Fig. 9. The variation of k_2 with $[\text{H}^+]$ at 30 °C.

A variation in pH showed the rate to increase on increasing pH in agreement with inverse dependence of rate on $[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 10). Thus, the rate law on including $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$, $[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ dependences becomes eq. (10).

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_3[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2[\text{H}^+]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

The value of k_3 at 30 °C was found to be 8.8×10^{-2} L² mol⁻² s⁻¹. By determining k_1 in air (20% O_2) and O_2 -saturated solution, order in O_2 was found to be 0.90 which can be taken as unity. The values of R_{obs} in air-saturated

Fig. 10. The plot of $[S^{IV}]$ vs time at $[Pd^{II}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $[S^{IV}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $[C_6H_4] = 5.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $pH = 5.22$ and $t = 30^\circ \text{C}$.

and O_2 -saturated solutions were found to be $8.33 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively. The complete law then becomes

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_4 [Pd^{II}] [S^{IV}]^2 [O_2] [H^+]^{-1} \quad (11)$$

The value of overall empirical energy of activation was found to be 74 kJ mol^{-1} .

Effect of ammonia : Oxidation of sulfur(IV) by O_2 is known to follow a radical mechanism involving oxysulfur radicals, viz. SO_3^- , SO_4^- and SO_4^{2-} as reactive intermediates. Several organics are known to inhibit this reaction through scavenging of sulfate ion radical, SO_4^- . Recently ammonia has been shown to inhibit this reaction¹⁸ when $pH \geq 7.0$. So the effect of ammonia on the reaction rate can be used test for operation of radical mechanism involving oxysulfur radicals. Based on this premise, the effect of ammonia was investigated by varying its concentration in the range, $(0.1-1.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ at $pH 9.0$, and found to have no effect on Pd^{II} -catalyzed sulfur(IV) autoxidation. This rules out the operation of a radical mechanism in Pd^{II} -catalysis.

Effect of ethanol : The effect of well known inhibitor for sulfur(IV) autoxidation⁵, that is, ethanol was examined in both acidic ($pH 5.22$) and alkaline media ($pH 9.0$). At $pH 5.22$, ethanol was found to inhibit the autoxidation. These data were treated in terms of well known eq. (12) for inhibition and the value of inhibition parameter, C was found to be 2.1×10^2 .

$$R_{\text{aut}} = R_0 / (1 + C [\text{Inh}]) \quad (12)$$

where R_{aut} is the rate of in the presence of ethanol, R_0 is

the rate of in the absence of ethanol, $[\text{Inh}]$ is the concentration of inhibitor and C is the empirical inhibition parameter.

The study of the ethanol effect at $pH 9.0$ showed initially $[\text{ethanol}]$ up to $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ to have no effect. Only when still higher concentrations $((2-5) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1})$ were used the inhibiting effect became noticeable. The value of C was found to be 0.65×10^{-2} .

For sulfur(IV)-autoxidation operating through oxysulfur radicals, the reported C values lie in the range, $(2.5 \times 10^3 - 2.4 \times 10^4)^{27}$ and the $[\text{ethanol}]$ needed to completely stop the reaction is $\leq 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. In the present study such a small ethanol concentration has only a small effect and much higher $[\text{ethanol}]$ is needed to have sizable inhibiting effect. Thus the relatively low values of C , and the necessity of much higher $[\text{ethanol}]$ to stop the reaction rule out the operation of a radical mechanism in Pd^{II} -catalyzed reaction, and the observed small inhibition effect could be due to blocking of coordination sites on Pd^{II} through competitive coordination by ethanol or any other similar effects for which large number of possibilities exist. The oxidation of ethanol by O_2 catalyzed by palladium is well known²⁸.

Effect of benzene : Benzene is generally a stronger inhibitor than ethanol for sulfur(IV) autoxidation reaction⁵. The benzene affected the reaction rate in a peculiar way; it introduced an induction period, the length of which increased with increase in $[\text{benzene}]$. Beyond induction period the reaction occurred at almost the same rate at different $[\text{benzene}]$. However, this rate was less than the rate under the same reaction conditions without benzene. An interesting kinetics run was performed as follows. A run was started in presence of $5.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ benzene. The reaction remained shut up to 20 min and there after the reaction started own its own. Again after 45 min from the start of the reaction, benzene was added and interestingly the reaction stopped but restarted after about 60 min from the original time. 15 min after this, benzene was again added, the reaction again stopped by restarted after 90 min from the original time as shown in Fig. 11. This experiment clearly shows that till benzene remains in the reaction mixture. The reaction remains shut and as soon as benzene is consumed by chemical reaction and/or removed by evaporation (possible because the reaction was carried out in open vessel with continuous stirring)

the reaction restarts. This indicates the benzene somehow blocks the reaction between sulfur(IV) and O₂. Quite likely benzene blocks the coordination sites on Pd^{II} and hinders the coordination of O₂. Indeed, benzene is known to form a complex with palladium(II)²⁹, and its palladium(II)-catalyzed oxidation by O₂ is also well known³⁰.

Discussion

On the basis of our spectrophotometric results, and the work of Mahal and van Eldik^{14,16}, it can be surmised that palladium(II) in our reaction conditions exists mainly as [Pd(SO₃)₂]²⁻ and [Pd(SO₃)₃]⁴⁻. Further, absence of appreciable effect of [buffer] and [chloride] on absorbance, *k*₁, *k*₂, *k*₃ and the autoxidation rate shows that no acetate or chloride ions are present in the first coordination sphere of these two sulfitepalladium(II) complexes. In view of well known square planer geometry and coordination number four of these complexes, these can be formulated as [Pd(H₂O)₂(SO₃)₂]²⁻ and [Pd(H₂O)(SO₃)₃]⁴⁻. However, in the subsequent discussion, H₂O molecules have been omitted for the sake of simplicity. It may be mentioned that the complex [Pd(SO₃)₂]²⁻ may exist in *cis* or *trans* or in both forms.

In the pH range of this study, sulfur(IV) will largely exist as HSO₃⁻ with small fraction as SO₃²⁻ governed by the eq. (12).

Before presenting the mechanism, it is worth recalling that in many metal catalyzed autoxidation studies, the involvement of ternary reactive intermediate of the type {(O₂)(M)([S^{IV}]₂)} type has been suggested¹². The formation of such a complex may be a priori for catalytic autoxidation following a non-radical pathway. Since the palladium(II) is known to undergo a two-electron change, the possibility of formation of oxysulfur radicals is remote. This is further ruled out by the nature of effect of ammonia, ethanol and benzene. On the basis of these arguments and the kinetic results obtained in this study, the following reaction sequence can be proposed.

The forward rate constants, *k*₁, *k*_{II}, *k*_{III} for Scheme 1, determined from stopped flow studies, are much larger than the rate constants for autoxidation reaction which due its slowness has been studied using conventional technique. It is, therefore, assumed that equilibria (13–15) are rapidly established as compared to the step (15) which involves the electron transfer culminating in the oxidation of sulfur(IV). As *k*_{II} is independent of [S^{IV}], pH, [O₂], [buffer], it must represent some sort of isomerisation reaction (Scheme 1). It appears that the attack of HSO₃⁻ on [(O₂)Pd(SO₃)₂]²⁻ produces O-bonded complex which isomerizes into S-bonded complex. The present reaction appears to be redox controlled as the rate of autoxidation is much slower than the rate of substitution reactions (13–14).

Assuming that the equilibria (12–15) are rapidly established, the following rate law may be derived.

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = kK_{d_2}K_1K_2K_3[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2[\text{O}_2] / \{ [\text{H}^+](1 + K_1K_{d_2}[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}][\text{H}^+]^{-1} + K_1K_2K_{d_2}[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}][\text{O}_2][\text{H}^+]^{-1} + K_1K_2K_3K_{d_2}[\text{O}_2][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2[\text{H}^+]^{-1}) \} \quad (17)$$

As the reaction displays a first order in [O₂] and as the absorbance of palladium(II)-sulfur(IV) in solutions is not affected by presence of O₂, the inequality {*K*₁*K*₂*K*_{*d*2}[S^{IV}][O₂][H⁺]⁻¹ + *K*₁*K*₂*K*_{*d*2}[O₂][S^{IV}]²[H⁺]⁻¹} < < {1 + *K*₁*K*_{*d*2}[S^{IV}][H⁺]⁻¹} appears to hold and then the rate law (21) reduces to

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = kK_{d_2}K_1K_2K_3[\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2[\text{O}_2] / \{ [\text{H}^+](1 + K_1K_{d_2}[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}][\text{H}^+]^{-1}) \} \quad (18)$$

Since the values of the term, *K*₁*K*_{*d*2}[H⁺]⁻¹[S^{IV}] < < 1, the rate law (18) reduces to experimental rate law (11). The mechanism explains the first order in [O₂], observed both from autoxidation and stopped flow studies, and other kinetics features such as dependences on [Pd^{II}] and pH.

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